

Supplementary material

MONOPTEROS isoform MP11ir plays a role during somatic embryogenesis in *Arabidopsis thaliana*

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Supplementary Table S1. Expression levels of *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8*.

Supporting information for Figure 5. Data indicate the relation expression values \pm SD as specified in the legend of Figure 5

Line	Day	<i>TAA1</i>	<i>TAR1</i>	<i>YUC3</i>	<i>YUC5</i>	<i>YUC8</i>
<i>proXVE:ΔARF5</i> <i>proDR5:GFP</i>	1d	1.74±0.09	27.83±16.03	1.04±0.45	11.69±5.87	16.58±6.22
	5d	0.83±0.11	0.92±0.43	2.20±0.12	1.21±0.35	5.75±0.69
	10d	1.46±0.25	0.73±0.61	0.46±0.05	2.47±0.54	0.97±0.17
<i>pro35S:bdl-GR</i>	5d	0.22±0.05	0.04±0.03	0.03±0.03	1.70±0.26	0.10±0.02
	10d	0.23±0.11	0.05±0.04	0.03±0.02	2.43±1.16	0.13±0.08
<i>mpS319</i>	0d	0.56±0.34	0.04±0.13	0.17±0.14	0.34±0.19	0.04±0.01
	10d	0.20±0.16	0.05±0.17	0.32±0.25	0.09±0.05	0.25±0.15
<i>mpS319</i>	5d	0.15±0.07	0.12±0.09	0.02±0.03	0.02±0.02	0.05±0.08
	10d	0.20±0.16	0.65±0.17	0.32±0.25	0,09±0,05	0.25±0.15
<i>proMP:MP</i> <i>mpS319</i>	5d	1.25±0.30	0.95±0.60	1.63±0.55	0.95±0.57	1.12±0.70
	10d	0.83±0.38	0.48±0.15	1.40±0.24	3,55±1,60	0.88±0.32
<i>proMP:MP11ir</i> <i>mpS319</i>	5d	1.62±0.07	0.86±0.50	0.53±0.07	0.68±0.69	0.61±0.26
	10d	0.64±0.06	0.11±0.10	0.67±0.16	2,14±0,81	0.35±0.07
<i>proMP:MP11ir</i> <i>proMP:MP</i> <i>mpS319</i>	5d	1.03±0.38	0.30±0.19	1.40±0.48	1.28±0.83	0.98±0.56
	10d	1.30±0.32	0.26±0.23	2.35±0.12	1,79±1,33	1.46±0.29

Supplementary Table S2. The primers used in experiments.

Primers used in RT-qPCR/PCR analysis of <i>TF</i> and <i>YUC</i> genes				
Gene	ID	pF 5'-3'	pR 5'-3'	Publication
<i>MP11ir</i>	<i>AT1G19850</i>	TGGGTAATGTTTGGACTTGG	CCACAAACTCTCCCATGGAT	Cucinotta et al., 2021
<i>MP</i>	<i>AT1G19850</i>	CACTAAGGTTCAAAAACCG	TTACGCATCCACAAACTCTTC	Wójcikowska and Gaj, 2017
<i>TIN</i>	<i>AT4G27090</i>	GTCGTTATCGTCGACGTTGTT	CCTCGATCAAAGCCTTCTTCT	Wójcikowska et al., 2013
<i>TAA1</i>	<i>AT1G70560</i>	TTCGTGGTCAATCTGGATCATGG	ACCACGTATCGTCACCGTACAC	
<i>TAR1</i>	<i>AT1G23320</i>	CGCAGCGGTTCTTATTACTCCAC	TTGTCGAACGTCCTTGCGTCTC	Present work
<i>TAR2</i>	<i>AT4G24670</i>	GCTCTTCACTGCTTCAAAGAGCAC	TCTGTCTTTCACCAAAGCCCATCC	
<i>YUC1</i>	<i>AT4G32540</i>	CGGAACACCGTTCATGTGT	CCGGTGACATTTTTCAGCTC	Wójcikowska et al., 2013
<i>YUC2</i>	<i>AT4G13260</i>	TTGTGGTTCGTGACTCGGTA	TTCAAGAGGGCCAAGTTTTG	
<i>YUC3</i>	<i>AT1G04610</i>	GATGGCCGTGTTCTTGAGAT	TCATGAGCCACACTCATAGC	
<i>YUC4</i>	<i>AT5G11320</i>	AACTCCCGTTCTTGATGTCG	AAAAACTATTCTCCTTAAGCCAATC	
<i>YUC5</i>	<i>AT5G43890</i>	TGTCCAGTCTGCTCGATACG	TTCTCGCCGATTTGTACTC	
<i>YUC6</i>	<i>AT5G25620</i>	GGTAAACTCCGGTTCTCGAC	TTGGAAATCCATCTTCTTACTAAAC	
<i>YUC7</i>	<i>AT2G33230</i>	TGAAGAACACCGCAGGTA	CCAAGTCGTTTTCCTTAAGCC	
<i>YUC8</i>	<i>AT4G28720</i>	CGTCTCAAGCTTCACTTCC	AGCCACTGGTCTCATCGAAC	
<i>YUC9</i>	<i>AT1G04180</i>	TGGTCGTTAGAAGCTCGGTT	CGGCGTCTTCTGTGCAT	
<i>YUC10</i>	<i>AT1G48910</i>	TTACCGGAAAAGCTCCTGTC	TCACGTATTCATAGTCTCTAACCA	
<i>YUC11</i>	<i>AT1G21430</i>	GAGAATGGCGAAGGTGTGAT	TAACACGTGCACCTGGCTAC	

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Supplementary Figure S1. *MP11ir* is expressed during somatic embryogenesis.

Presence of *MP11ir* transcript during plant development *in vivo* and auxin-dependent SE induction *in vitro* (5.0 μ M 2,4-D). IZE – immature zygotic embryo; SE – somatic embryogenesis; 5d – 5th day of SE induction; 10d – 10th day of SE induction; gDNA – genomic DNA; nc – negative control; *TIN* – reference gene. Created with BioRender.com.

Supplementary Figure S2. The induction of somatic embryogenesis depends on 2,4-D and NAA, but not IAA.

The capacity of IZE explants cultured for three weeks on media with different 2,4-D (**A, D-G**), NAA (**B, H-K**), and IAA (**C, L-O**) concentrations: 0.0 (**D, H, L**), 2.5 (**E, I, M**), 5.0 (**F, J, N**), and 7.5 μM (**G, K, O**); ($n = 3$; means \pm SD are presented). IZE explants cultured on auxin-free medium developed seedlings after three weeks of culture (**D, H, L**). The increasing embryogenic capacity of the Col-0 IZE explants cultured for three weeks on media with different 2,4-D or NAA concentrations (2.5 (**E, I**), 5.0 (**F, J**), and 7.5 μM (**G, K**)). The weak embryogenic capacity of the Col-0 IZE explants cultured for three weeks on media with different IAA concentrations (2.5 (**M**), 5.0 (**N**), and 7.5 μM (**O**)). The white arrowhead indicates the somatic embryo. Size bars indicate 1 mm. 2,4-D – 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid; IAA – indole-3-acetic acid; IZE – immature zygotic embryo; NAA – 1-naphthaleneacetic acid.

Supplementary Figure S3. Expression level of auxin biosynthetic genes in *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* somatic embryos.

(A-C) Relative expression level of auxin biosynthesis genes in the 1- (A), 5- (B), and 10-day-old (C) embryogenic cultures of the *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* transgenic line treated with 1 μM β-estradiol (+E). The relative expression level was normalized to internal control (*AT4G27090*) and calibrated to the *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* culture of the same age and untreated with 1 μM β-estradiol (-E). Value significantly different from the *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* (-E) culture of the same age is marked with asterisks (Student's t-test, * $p < 0.05$; $n = 3$; means \pm SD are presented). Gray bars indicate no statistical differences, white bars indicate that the gene is upregulated when $\Delta ARF5$ is induced, and black bars when the gene expression is reduced.

Supplementary Figure S4. Analysis of the *TAA1*, *TAR1*, and *YUC* promoters for MP binding sites.

(A) The *TAA1*, *TAR*, and *YUC* gene promoters were analyzed for MP and ARF2 binding sites.

(B) Binding regions detected by DAP-seq in (O'Malley et al., 2016) TGTCnn sequences. (C) The presence of AuxRe element based on the PlantPan 4.0 database.

Supplementary Figure S5. Expression pattern of TAA1, TAR1, TAR2, and YUC1-11 during somatic embryogenesis induction.

(A) Spatio-temporal localization of TAA1, TAR1, TAR2, and YUC1-11 enzymes during SE process under *in vitro* culture. (B-F) Map of TAA1, TAR1, TAR2, YUC1-11 enzymes involved in auxin biosynthesis in IZE explants of reporter lines (B), and explants cultured on E5 medium and on 3- (C), 5- (D), 10- (E), 15-day-old (F) *in vitro* culture. Images were digitally extracted for comparison. Size bars indicate 100 μm (A). Summary drawings were prepared using BioRender. IZE – immature zygotic embryo; SE – somatic embryogenesis.

Figure S6. Overexpressing $\Delta ARF5$ increases the level of endogenous indolic compounds. Level of indolic compounds ($\mu\text{g/g}$ of fresh tissue) in 3-week-old IZE-culture of *proXVE::\Delta ARF5 proDR5::GFP* transgenic line with $1 \mu\text{M}$ β -estradiol-induced $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression. Size bars indicate 1 mm. The data are presented as a boxplot. The cross represents the mean value; the center line represents the median value; the box limits are upper and lower quartiles; the whiskers show the 1.5x interquartile range; the open circles are outliers. The value in *proXVE::\Delta ARF5 proDR5::GFP* (+E) is significantly different from the *proXVE::\Delta ARF5 proDR5::GFP* (-E) culture of the same age is marked with asterisks ($*p < 0.05$; $n = 5$; Student's t-test). The images illustrate the type of samples and are identical to those used in Figure 4C, bottom row. IZE – immature zygotic embryo.

Supplementary Figure S7. Effects of repressing auxin biosynthesis in *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* during somatic embryogenesis induction.

The effect of auxin biosynthesis inhibitor yucasin on the SE efficiency (A) and productivity (B) of the Col-0 (C-H) and *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* (I-N) IZE explants. The capacity of Col-0 and *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* IZE explants cultured for three weeks on E5 media with different yucasin concentrations: 0 (C, D, I, J), 100 (E, F, K, L), and 150 μM (G, H, M, N), supplemented (D, F, H, J, L, N) or not (C, I, E, K, G, M) with 1 μM estradiol (+E) for induction of *ΔARF5* overexpression; (n = 3; means ± SD are presented). A representative image of the plates is shown in the bottom row. A representative image of a somatic embryo is shown in the top row. In insets (L, N), alternative phenotypes are shown. Col-0 IZE explants cultured on control media (E5 and E5 + E) developed numerous somatic embryos after three weeks of culture (C, D). Different yucasin concentrations resulted in the decreasing embryogenic capacity of the Col-0 IZE explants cultured for three weeks on E5 and E5 + E media (A, B, E-H). The embryogenic capacity of the *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* IZE explants cultured for three weeks on E5 media (A, B, I) is comparable to Col-0 IZE explants (C). Explants with *ΔARF5*-overexpression (E5 + E) lack a SE response (J). Different yucasin concentrations resulted in a decrease in the embryogenic capacity of the *proXVE:ΔARF5 proDR5:GFP* IZE explants cultured for three weeks on E5 media with (A, B, K, M). Explants overexpressing

ΔARF5 (+E) cultured on E5 media supplemented with yucasin at different concentrations were capable, but with very low efficiency and productivity, to regenerate somatic embryos. They mostly produced callus (**A, B, L, N**). Size bars indicate 1 mm for explant images and 1 cm for plate images. E – estradiol; IZE – immature zygotic embryo; SE – somatic embryogenesis.